

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE FUTURE OF DIGITALIZATION: A NEW POSSIBILITIES FOR DEMOCRACY OR A REVIVAL OF TOTALITARIAN PRACTICES?

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to present what digitalization is today, as well as what advantages and risks it carries in the context of the transformation of political systems. The author will also try to understand who benefits more from digitalization - civil society or the state?

Keywords: digitalization, digitalization of politics, democracy, e-government, fluid democracy, direct democracy, civil society.

In the modern world, digitalization is becoming more widespread, affecting more and more processes, including social ones. Initially concerned only with the technical aspect of human life, informatization has begun to change society in the last 30 years. Especially the situation changed with the spread of the Internet, which made it possible to bring the possibilities of communication to an unprecedented level. We see that human life has become much more convenient, and new drivers have appeared for the development of democratic processes. But what if digitalization does not serve the development of democracy, but, on the contrary, allows the state to concentrate in its hands huge real powers to manage society? To what extent is such a situation possible? It is these questions that the author asks, wanting to understand what challenges humanity should prepare for as a social organism.

To understand what to expect from digitalization in the social and political sphere, we should first define such basic concepts as democracy and digitalization.

It should be said that the term democracy is currently used in several senses. First, the most popular at the moment is the definition of democracy as a way of organizing decision-making. However, besides it, democracy is often used in the sense of a political regime (along with authoritarianism and totalitarianism). Also, democracy is sometimes used in a modern or in an obsolete (antique or medieval) sense, but this division is not so important for us. In this paper, the term democracy will be used precisely as a way of making decisions. Democracy is a political system based on the collective decision-making on a particular issue. In contrast to the concept of a republic (as a form of government), it is very important for democracy that the impact of the participants in the process be as equal as possible. At the moment, "ideal" democracies do not exist, due to the technical limitations. However, now in Western countries the most common system is liberal democracy, the essence of which is the combination of democratic ideals with the values of individuality, economic freedom and the rule of law. Such systems, in addition to the above, also have a system of checks and balances that does not allow the majority to suppress the minority. Representative democracy is a form of government that reflects modern Western democracy.

It assumes that voters vote for certain candidates representing their interests in the legislative branch of the state. In recent decades, there has been a growing critique of representative democracy among thinkers both on the left and right, claiming that it is obsolete, and proposing new forms of government, which we will discuss next.

Now it is necessary to define what digitalization is. Digitalization is the process of introducing digital technologies into a particular system in order to speed up its work, improve ease of use, and, as a result, increase efficiency. The system here can be very diverse, from commercial projects to state enterprises. In our case, by the system we mean society and the state, therefore, digitalization will affect the political, economic, cultural spheres of society. For example, at the moment in Russia, one of the main directions for the development of digitalization is its introduction into the educational process; in the process of providing social services to the population. In addition, the agenda for introducing digitalization into public life is becoming especially noticeable and debatable in the issue of using electronic forms of voting in elections.

Now let's move on to the opportunities that digitalization opens up for the development of democracy. What in this case could we mean by development? First of all, it means bringing the practice of democracy closer to its ideal: direct democracy. It is a set of measures to involve people in the political process; increasing the role of their voice; the ability of people to solve an increasing number of issues without government control. In addition, there is a separate area related to society - this is the development of security technologies, the purpose of which is to reduce the level of crime, but this topic will be discussed separately below.

In general, if we talk about the impact of digitalization on democracy in more general terms, it is first of all we must mention the impact of the Internet on the social communications. As we know, this technology allows you to transfer data almost instantly from anywhere in the world over great distances. All this could not but transform the political landscape of existing societies. The development of the Internet has radically changed the scheme of mobilization of supporters by political parties. Now for organization of various party

events (rallies, congresses, meeting, etc.), the participants do not even need to see each other. In particular, this, of course, applies to meeting and protests. In this context, it must be said that protest activity is influenced not only by the speed of protest organization, but also by the speed with which news about some trigger is spread throughout society. Today, any unfortunate or unpopular government decision can lead demonstrators to administrative buildings on the very same evening. Moreover, now opposition-minded citizens can discuss the actions of their government with other people without event leaving their homes, without meeting with anyone. And the US presidential elections in November 2020 showed us that sometimes what happens on social networks has a much greater political impact than what happens in real life. The January 2021 "storming" of the Capitol by radical supporters of Donald Trump is no exception – such coordination would have been impossible without associations in social networks. However, what is described above is more general reasoning.

In more concrete terms, the system of representative democracy has come under increasing criticism in recent decades. It is argued that it is not capable of reflecting the diverse interests of the entire spectrum of citizens - and we live in a time when, in the context of globalization, the social diversity of societies is increasing. So, democracy needs variations that will allow for the largest number of votes to be taken into account. There is, for example, a development of the delegative democracy called liquid democracy. Liquid democracy is a subspecies of delegative democracy, which is a form of democratic control over the government. According to this concept, the people give power not to representatives (as in a representative democracy), but to delegates. Each person has the right to vote on each issue directly, or to delegate his vote to another person if he considers him more competent. In turn, these persons can elect another delegate from themselves (the so-called "meta-delegation"). This delegation can be either absolute (on all issues) or relative (in certain areas). The same differences exist in the time of delegation. The supposed benefit of such a concept lies in the increased responsibility of voters, since they feel involved in politics. The main difference from representative democracy is that delegates can be recalled at any time. In theory, every person in such a system can be a delegate.

In this case, the concept of direct democracy is also undergoing a rather serious development - this is a type of democracy in which citizens are directly involved in making decisions on certain issues (including those of national importance), and, no less important, they can initiate them. In our time, direct democracy is basically an atavism in most states, although, for example, Switzerland has retained it to a very large extent, although it is noted that in large states it is very difficult to widely apply this concept. However, with the development of the Internet, the concept of electronic democracy, or e-democracy, has appeared. Its essence lies in the application of technological advances and increased communication in solving various issues, both at the district level and at state level. Without any doubt, the Internet makes direct democracy much more real than it was before. If, for example, until now the problem here was the organization of referendums on

any issue (and its cost), now the conditional "electronic sites" are much cheaper in organization and maintenance. In addition, according to the developers of the concept, the idea is to minimize the possibility of vote rigging. This statement is based on the fact that the counting of votes will be done by a computer that will always be impartial, which means that the elections will be as transparent and fair as possible.

It should be noted that in addition to improving democracy, the development of its electronic forms has another important mission - it is the "expansion" of democracy. Thus, it is believed that the clarity and structure of the electronic system will not allow it to be changed at the needs of politicians. This, on the one hand, will affect the system's greater focus on citizens, and on the other hand, it will seriously complicate the possibility of coups d'état and changes in the Constitution in favor of the ruling elites.

Also, in addition to new concepts of democracy, the idea of electronic government (e-government) is very popular (and is already being implemented in many countries). In general, its essence is very accessible and understandable - this is the digitalization of the activities of executive authorities, designed to increase the efficiency of its activities and accelerate the provision of services to various groups of the population. For example, in Estonia back in 2000, parliamentary meetings completely got rid of the paper form of documents, and by 2010, 92% of all tax returns began to be filed electronically. Currently, in most developed and many developing countries, citizens can receive almost the entire range of public services via the Internet, including contacting the relevant authorities with a demand to protect their rights; appeals to authorities; various petitions of a political and economic nature. For example, we have survey about digitalization solving problems of corruption, which compare benefits and limitations of e-government in this sphere.

Authors came to conclusion [1], that technologies itself doesn't solve corruption problems, but they can give some benefits, such as: greater access to government data and its transparency; it reduces number of interactions between society and government, which lead to bureaucracy reducing; transparency of system lead to grow of social trust, which is mostly important in case of digitalization. Experts note that the most important thing on the way to e-government is the digitalization of the NSO [2] (National Statistics Offices), since statistics should become more transparent and accessible to all users. This is, among other things, a very important step towards the participation of citizens in the discussion of government performance.

Continuing the theme of trust, it should be noted that trust in digitalization varies greatly in different countries. For example, surveys show that despite the prevalence of Internet infrastructure in developed countries, trust in the growth of digitalization in them can vary significantly [3]. At the same time, many survey participants are concerned about how much their government will use these technologies. We have a fact, that at the moment the most important issue in promoting digitalization is the growth of confidence in this process. However, unfortunately, digitalization, in addition to the obvious advantages in the field of improving democracy, also has obvious disadvantages. And these shortcomings, according to the author, are no less

significant than the advantages, and even pose a certain threat to the existing order.

First of all, it is worth noting that at the beginning we noted a number of advantages that digitalization brings. What was meant was how these advantages can be used by societies and each individual individually in order to defend public or personal interests before the state. However, we did not talk about what benefits the development of the Internet brings specifically for the state. To generalize, the state can use digitalization to its advantage just as well as society, if not better. Like citizens, the state gets at its disposal a system capable of instantly transmitting any messages (orders, orders, appointments) to anywhere in the world. The state, like society, can now function on public unrest not only by material methods, but also by certain information companies, designed to both calm the public and direct it in the right direction.

In addition, it was mentioned above how digitalization affects the public safety system. Undoubtedly, digital systems being introduced into the tools of the police, prosecutors and special services have comprehensively increased the security of ordinary citizens. The ubiquity of video recording systems allows a person to be absolutely calm at any time of the day, even in unfamiliar places. For criminals who have already committed an offense, it has now become much more difficult to escape, and their threat to society is minimized. The ubiquitous tracking of purchases and customs makes it possible to stop terrorist threats at an early stage of their organization. A face recognition system has already been created and is being implemented in some states, which also helps to prevent offenses. That is, to summarize briefly, digitalization makes it possible to minimize, and even completely overcome crime in a very foreseeable future.

However, the state, unlike society, is a much more organized system, with a much more distant planning horizon. Therefore, there are certain concerns about how the state decides to dispose of expanding opportunities. It should be understood that the basis of the activities of civil society and modern democracy in general is control over the state. In other words, it means that the state is an independent bureaucratic system that has its own interests, and these interests often run counter to the interests of society. It is from this premise that the assumption follows that the state can use digitalization to establish control over society. In addition, one of the foundations of a totalitarian regime (in its classical interpretation) is state control over all spheres of people's lives. And if in the past this point could not be fully implemented, now we see that the state has every opportunity to implement a system for monitoring society.

An outstanding example, according to some researchers, is now China. The specificity of this country lies in the fact that, unlike Western democracies, it has never declared the strong rights of the individual, so a system of control over society can be built there relatively easily from a normative point of view. However, if we move away from formal features, China has already made significant progress in the systems of remote control of society. The so-called. The "social rating system", which has been the subject of heated discussion on the Internet for more than one year, both among ordinary people and among experts. It also spawned a huge number of memes that make fun of the

Chinese control system. In short, the social rating system allows the state to control human behavior through a number of incentives, such as economic symbols. Under this system, a person with a low social rating, for example, may not be approved for a loan - and this is only one of the easiest sanctions. In addition, in China, the government, for example, can limit the time spent on the Internet or in online games by citizens, although these measures cannot be called unambiguously negative. Nevertheless, we see that China, as an authoritarian state, with the development of digitalization, has received more and more opportunities to control not only public opinion, but literally over the citizens. Of course, we are not talking about a digital dictatorship, which is still difficult to build due to the lack of resources of states, but with the political will, this lack can be quickly compensated.

In addition, Chinese courts are now undergoing a process of digitalization, the goal of which is to teach AI to pass sentences on a number of uncomplicated articles. Such a system, as conceived by the authorities, should significantly optimize the work of the courts. However, researchers have their own concerns about this [4]. According to them, in itself such an idea is good, especially if it is carried out for the convenience of citizens. The situation is quite different, according to them, in a situation where there is a practice of punitive legal proceedings. In this case, digitalization can only become an extension of repressive tools.

In addition to means of direct control, it should be understood that digitalization significantly expands the possibilities of state propaganda. It is known that in many states, including democratic ones, there are entire departments for information special operations and the so-called "troll factories". The task of such departments is quite clear - it is necessary to create the impression of a certain public opinion on a particular problematic issue. All this leads to the fact that a person is deliberately misinformed in one direction or another, and this may further influence his political views. Moreover, according to Elon Musk, after buying the social network Twitter, it turned out that a huge number of network users are bots. What these bots did on the social network remains to be seen, but it should be borne in mind that Twitter is an incredibly influential social network, where the core of socio-political discussions in Western (and not only) countries is concentrated, many heads of state have their pages there and actively fill them.

However, one should not think that the threat of "digital dictatorship" threatens only China or developing authoritarian countries. This threat always persists in the West. At the moment, the concept of remote voting is actively developing in developed countries. So far, this system in most countries exists only in the form of voting by mail, and where voting is carried out literally using the Internet, it exists only as part of an experiment on relatively small groups of voters. Nevertheless, we see that in the largest and most traditional democracy, the United States, during the last presidential elections, confidence in such a procedure has fallen sharply. Of course, this phenomenon is greatly complicated by the American specifics of the polarization of political views, but we see the fact that people are still not ready for non-traditional types of voting. However, mail-in voting may be questioned, as the counts will still be carried out by election commission officials. At the same time, when using electronic voting systems, it

is much more difficult to challenge their results - the authorities assure citizens that the program counted the votes, which means that it could not falsify the elections.

Also, very strong disputes in society (almost all over the world, but especially in the West) were caused by the policies of developed countries during the acute stage of the Covid-19 pandemic. Many developed countries called for citizens to be vaccinated, but formally this was not a compulsory procedure. In fact, a person who had not been vaccinated was significantly limited in his abilities - he could not work, be in public catering establishments, etc. But the fact that the data on the vaccinated were entered in a single electronic register caused unrest for many citizens. Many countries also introduced "vaccination passports" that provided normal access to public goods.

Here you can also recall the anti-utopian theme of the "rise of the machines", which was devoted to such famous film series as the Matrix or the Terminator. Of course, such a scenario is still difficult to implement, since, according to scientists, for its implementation it is necessary to develop a strong artificial intelligence, while humanity is hardly able to create a weak one. However, the Western techno community has been under the strongest impression of ChatGPT in recent weeks. This is a question-and-answer program that is able to answer almost any question based on open data. The peculiarity of the system is that it is able to solve problems of great complexity, for example, to write programs of medium complexity.

However, it is fair to say that in developed countries there is a discussion about the limits of digitalization and influences decision-making. So, for example, in September 2022, a number of European Union agencies called for a ban on the use of artificial intelligence for a face recognition system in order to preserve the privacy of citizens. In addition, it is worth remembering that in democratic countries, as a rule, there is a very complex system of decision-making. It goes without saying that fundamental initiatives will, one way or another, be discussed, during which the most harmful of them could be significantly mitigated.

OECD experts currently believe [5] that the main barrier to digitalization is not only the poor availability of high-speed Internet in developing and poor countries, but also the decline in confidence in the digital systems of the state in developed countries. To do this, it is necessary to develop digital literacy of people, to raise the level of general education. All this is necessary to combat the allegations that digitalization leads to total surveillance and election fraud at all levels. In addition, it is extremely important not to limit the freedom of speech, because the discussion must remain open. They also think that democracy can significantly benefit from digitalization if it can prove its effectiveness in solving a number of problems, such as: increasing voters' access to elections; protection of electoral companies; nurturing democratic deliberation [6].

What is the most likely future if current trends continue? In fact, it is quite difficult to answer this question, again, due to the fact that digitalization in politics is two multidirectional processes. On the one hand, we have the strengthening of civil society, on the other, the state apparatus. According to the author, a lot depends on two important factors: firstly, traditional democratic systems should not lose citizens' trust in electoral processes, and their changes should be clearly controlled by society and transparent; secondly, of course, a lot depends on what type of systems "win" in the race of progress. If it is China with its system, then for many states the truth will become obvious that this system is more advanced in terms of the evolution of governance, and democracy cannot compete in efficiency with digital dictatorships. This is, of course, largely about the economic and technological aspect, but digitalization will improve the methods of state violence, which will also increase the stability of existing systems. However, according to the author, the last 10 years have shown that the systems of control over the public mind they have advanced significantly in their effectiveness, while the tools of horizontal communication and network self-organization have received almost no new use.

Summing up, I would like to note once again that digitalization can become both the cause of a new "democratic wave" and the reason for the transition of humanity to more authoritarian methods of governance. In many ways, our future will be determined by who will show the best results in the next decades, but it is worth saying that at the moment, supporters of the system of control over society are making quite serious progress in this competition. In the coming years, innovations in the field of artificial intelligence await us, which will make the picture of our future clear.

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